

THE USE OF CARBON AND HYBRID WOVEN FABRICS IN EMERGENCY AIRCRAFT REPAIR WORK

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The development of wet-laminating methods of aircraft repair using carbon and hybrid fabrics has continued. It is shown that effective repairs may be made to painted aluminium-alloy surfaces provided that the paint is completely removed by abrasion. Good repairs are also possible on surfaces contaminated with hydraulic fluid, kerosene or water.

Tools for hand and power abrasion have been tested and alternative resin systems evaluated. It is shown that selected polyesters can give repair strengths consistently higher than those of metal plates fastened with 'pop' rivets at 15 mm spacing. Detailed descriptions are given of repairs to a helicopter drive shaft, to the fuselage and under-wing areas of a Canberra aircraft and to the barrel of a hydraulic jack.

An investigation has commenced into the control of fatigue cracks in light alloy by the use of bonded-on preformed carbon fibre fabric laminate patches. Complete crack arrest has been demonstrated, both in the laboratory and in ground-test on a Jetstream aircraft.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years the use of reinforced plastics to repair composite aircraft structures has become a topic of growing importance. Lubin [1], Foreman [2] and Myhre [3] for example have developed methods of making permanent repairs which aim to restore full design strength and stiffness to boron or carbon reinforced structures. Apart from the work of Baker et al [4] which examines the use of pre-formed unidirectional fibre-reinforced patches to arrest fatigue cracks, the use of composites to repair metal aircraft has not received similar attention, mainly because it was thought that such repairs would be neither permanent enough nor trustworthy enough to achieve the required standards of airworthiness.

Generally speaking, the aim of a repair should be to restore the aircraft to full design specification; and when time and well-equipped workshops are available this is normal procedure. However, there may be occasions when repairs must be done in the field in the shortest possible time, with minimal facilities and possibly adverse environmental conditions, simply to enable the aircraft to regain a base where full-standard repairs can be made. A previous paper [5] described application of emergency repairs of this type to holes in aircraft skins, using wet-laminating techniques. The advantages of these repairs over rivetted-on metal patches included their ability to accommodate double curvatures and differential thickness and the fact that they did not necessarily require a drill bit, without which rivetted repairs are virtually impossible.

The present paper describes further work on the repair of contaminated surfaces, suggests alternative resins and abrasion tools, and includes a preliminary evaluation of repairs made below room temperature. Detailed descriptions are given of a repair to a helicopter drive shaft, of field repairs in adverse conditions to the fuselage and wing of an aircraft, and of the repair of an aircraft hydraulic jack.

MATERIALS

Fabrics

It was earlier noted [5] that glass-fibre composites are not suitable as direct replacements for light alloy aircraft skins because their lower specific stiffness demands a thick patch and confers an unacceptable weight penalty. Fortunately, glass-carbon hybrid fabrics are now produced in U.K. in a wide range of weights and weaves, which can be chosen to suit the mechanical properties of the substrate and the requirements of the glue-line.

The fabric used in much of the earlier work was a 3:1 glass:carbon plain-weave hybrid (Fig 1), based on 5000-filament Morganite Type 2 carbon fibre. The fabric currently used to match L73 alloy is a 3:1 glass:carbon twill weave, based on 6000-filament Grafal EXAS, the twill weave producing a stronger laminate-to-substrate bond.

RESINS

The epoxy resin Epikote 828 cured with the fast room-temperature hardener Ancamine AC gave excellent results on uncontaminated surfaces at room temperature [5], but was difficult to use below 15°C because of its increased viscosity. The same disadvantage was found with an otherwise satisfactory alternative resin, designated ER2. Two low-viscosity resins containing reactive diluents were examined and rejected because of low heat distortion temperature in the final laminate, but a lower-viscosity variant of Epikote 828, designated Epikote 808 was evaluated and found to give reasonable strength in repair and to remain usable down to 10°C.

A number of room temperature curing agents were evaluated, including a mercaptan, designated 301B. It gave cure times of approximately six minutes at 20°C with good repair strengths but also had the disadvantage of high viscosity. The

tensile strengths of simulation-repairs using the more effective resin formulations are given in Table 1.

Polyester resins were not included in the early work on reinforced plastics repairs because they were expected to have poor adhesion and to be slow to cure at low temperatures. However, since they also have the potential advantages of low viscosity, higher heat distortion temperatures and tolerance to oily contaminants it was decided to evaluate some of the faster-curing formulations now available.

Among those examined Trylon AP101PA, Cellobond A260, Quickcure 1 and Quickcure 3 were found to combine fast cure with adequate strength in repair (Table 1); with methyl ethyl ketone peroxide catalyst, and a cobalt accelerator (where necessary) they gave gel times around 15 minutes at temperatures down to 0°C. Similar gel times at 0°C with faster rates of cure were obtained with benzoyl peroxide catalyst and dimethyl p-toluidine accelerator.

THE BASIC REPAIR METHOD

The basic stages of a repair are illustrated in Figs 2, 3 and 4. Fig 2 shows a hole in a section of aircraft skin. In Fig 3 the hole is shown bridged on the inner side with light-weight wire mesh held in place with the minimum number of 'pop' rivets, and with a layer of chopped strand mat tucked between the mesh and the edges of the hole to soak up excess resin. Fig 4 shows the component with a patch wet-laminated in place following a thorough abrasion round the hole to give good adhesion.

The patch shown in Fig 4 was made from three plies of hybrid fabric, feathered 12 mm back at each edge by the removal of free tows as in Fig 1 and applied in decreasing order of size as in Fig 5. The stiffness of a missing rib was restored by the addition of four plies of unidirectional carbon-fibre tape, also visible in Fig 4.

THE SIMULATION-REPAIR TEST

This procedure was devised to simulate an actual repair in order to provide realistic specimens for mechanical testing.

Two 150 mm-square panels of 1.22 mm-gauge L73 aluminium alloy are laid parallel and 75 mm apart in a bench-top jig, the gap simulating a hole in the skin of an aircraft. The panels are abraded back to a distance of 100 mm from the edges of the gap as in Fig 5. A 225 x 150 mm patch of hybrid fabric with the edges feathered (ie with the weft threads removed) 12 mm back from each end is laminated over the gap and the abraded areas, followed by three more patches of the same width but successively 25 mm shorter.

Two hours after starting the repair the laminate is cut lengthwise into six strips approximately 25 mm wide (to include exactly three carbon and nine glass tows in the case of 3:1 glass:carbon fabric). Two strips are tested in tension $2\frac{1}{4}$ hours after the start of the repair, two after 24 hours and the remaining two after 72 hours.

THE PREPARATION OF PAINTED SURFACES

Since the strength of a repair depends almost entirely on the adhesive bond between the patch and the substrate, preparation of the latter is all-important; nevertheless for emergency use such preparation must be simple and foolproof. Earlier work [5] had shown that abrasion down to the bare metal was adequate if done thoroughly, but that incompletely abraded paint gave a very poor bond. To investigate the dependence of bonding on the quality of abrasion, pairs of panels painted with acrylic paint and naturally weathered were given surface preparation ranging

from a solvent wipe to complete removal of the paint, and were simulation-repaired with 3:1 glass:carbon plain-weave hybrid fabric and Quickcure 3/Butanox M50 resin.

The results (Table 2) confirm that it is essential to remove all paint; this obviously applies to all paints and not just to acrylics, because there is no easy way of estimating the integrity of any aircraft paint in the field, even if it is reputed to adhere well.

To determine whether the arbitrary 100 mm patch overlap could be reduced to 75 mm without loss in strength a further series of simulation-repairs at room temperature was made and tested. The results are given in Table 3. Reducing the overlap made no significant difference to the epoxy specimens, but caused a reduction of the order of 20 per cent in the strength of the polyester specimens tested after 2 $\frac{1}{4}$ hours and a reduction of 10 per cent in the specimens tested after 24 hours. Only in the specimens tested after 72 hours was the effect non-significant. It was concluded that for maximum strength a 100 mm overlap is necessary.

ALTERNATIVE ABRADING TOOLS

Power abraders

The wire cupbrush used as the abrading tool in the early stages of the investigation was found to have a major disadvantage. Continuous operation in a non-reversing power tool bent the bristles away from the direction of rotation (Fig 6) and caused the panels to be polished rather than abraded. Since reversing power tools are not always available a number of alternatives to the brush were evaluated, including sanding discs with their flexible backing pads of different sizes, a proprietary rotary flail with replaceable coarse and fine flail wires, and a range of rotary flap wheels (Fig 7). The test criterion was the ease of abrading down to the bare metal a 60 mm x 60 mm square of the surface of a weathered polyurethane-painted aircraft component. The times taken are given in Table 4.

The results were conclusive; the flap wheels used at 2400 rev/min were easily the most efficient of the abraders. They cut fast and smoothly, rode projecting damage easily, and were self-dressing. The larger disc sander was moderately efficient, but missed small concavities and was not easy to control over projecting damage. The rotary flail scoured the substrate badly, was difficult to position on the work and, being unshielded and almost invisible when rotating, was considered very dangerous. The 80 mm x 30 mm 80 grade flap wheel at 2400 rev/min was adopted as the standard abradar for all subsequent work.

Hand abraders

When power is not available in an emergency, abrasion must be done by hand. Several hand abraders were evaluated, including a proprietary device, designated A in Table 4, with a plastics handgrip body and a metal face-plate to which an array of sharp rod-points were bonded (Fig 8). A similar device, designated B, comprised a metal face-plate to which metallic carbide granules were bonded, and a third device, designated C, was a rectangular foam block, faced with carborundum cloth. Each of these abraders was available in fine and coarse grades, and required frequent swirling in water to remove paint dust during use.

Device A was by far the most efficient of the three, and was later used effectively in a field repair.

CONTROL TESTING

Complementary to the control values previously published [5], lap-shear specimens 60 mm wide were made in 1.22 mm L73 sheet using three 4.75 mm diameter monel metal 'pop' rivets in stepped array, representing a section through a metal plate

repair fastened by two offset lines of rivets at 30 mm centres. The mean failing load in tension was 11.4 kN, equivalent to 6.0 kN per 23.5 mm of width. It is evident that almost all the values given in Tables 1,3 & 5 for simulation-repairs lie above this figure.

REPAIRS TO CONTAMINATED SURFACES

To obtain reasonable results with epoxy resins on surfaces contaminated with hydraulic fluid or aviation kerosene it was essential to use the resin wipe method 5 in which a coat of resin is painted on to the abraded area immediately prior to laminating and wiped off again to remove the contaminant. Even with this treatment a decrease in bond strength was observed in hydraulic-fluid contaminated repairs tested after 24 hours (Table 5), possibly due to the migration of the contaminant away from the glue-line where it may have been acting as a plasticizer.

The polyester resins, which are tolerant to small amounts of mineral oils, gave satisfactory bonds in simulated repair (Table 5) to oily surfaces with no pretreatment other than wiping excess oil from the substrate with a clean swab after abrasion.

To investigate the effect of water contamination, simulation-repairs were made in which, between the abrasion and the laminating stages each panel was flooded with tap-water and allowed to drain vertically for 15 seconds.

The results (Table 5) are not significantly different from those obtained from unwetted specimens (Table 1). It is concluded that the presence of water is not an important factor in short-term repairs at room temperature. An evaluation at freezing temperatures, where ice can form a physical barrier against adhesion, has not yet been undertaken.

REPAIRS BELOW ROOM TEMPERATURE

Table 6 gives the results of four simulation repairs below room temperature using one epoxy and two polyester resins and unidirectional 3:1 glass:carbon tape. The repairs were made and stored in the open air, at and below the temperatures stated, and were taken into the laboratory only at the time of test. The results appear satisfactory but are not an exact guide to behaviour, as it was subsequently found that with polyester resins the unidirectional fabric gives much higher bond strengths than the plain-weave fabric used in field repairs.

Further tests below room temperature are being carried out as part of an investigation of the fatigue properties of repairs.

THE REPAIR OF A HELICOPTER DRIVE SHAFT

An aluminium alloy tail rotor drive shaft was repaired as a demonstration exercise. The pretreatment was a simple abrasion down to the bare metal with a flap wheel, extending around the full circumference of the shaft between limits 80 mm each side of the damaged area (Fig 9) and requiring 21 minutes to complete.

Plain-weave 3:1 glass:carbon fabric was used, applied with the fibres at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the axis of the shaft to take the torsional loads. Because bias-woven hybrid fabrics and plain-weave fabrics wider than 560 mm were not at that time available a continuous wrap-round could not be provided; four separate patches were cut, each of the last three successively 25 mm narrower than the one before and of the correct length to butt-join around the tube and the preceding patches without deforming the $\pm 45^\circ$ alignment.

The laminating resin was Epikote 828:Amine T/100:20, chosen because it offered a pot life of 30 minutes compared with the 13 minutes of 828/Ancamine AC. A liberal coat was brushed on to the shaft, and the largest patch was wrapped round, brought to a butt joint and held in place by over-wrapping lightly with a spiral of sewing cotton. The three remaining patches were laminated-on in decreasing order of size and also held in place with sewing cotton, the four butt joints being arranged 90° out of phase around the shaft. The final patch was secured with a double overwrap of cotton, just visible in Fig 10, which also shows the outer butt joint.

The abrasion and laminating stages required 21 minutes to complete, and a further 10 minutes was required for the resin to gel.

THE REPAIR OF AN AIRCRAFT IN THE FIELD

The repair conditions

A Canberra aircraft was available with a 300 x 190 mm jagged hole in the fuselage aft of the port wing (Fig 11), and a clean rectangular 450 x 320 mm hole in the underside of the port wing (Fig 12). Immediately above the rectangular hole a portion of a rib had been cut away.

The repairs were made in the open air at 18°C ambient temperature, by a team of two operators working in intermittent heavy rain, with minimal equipment, and with no source of heat to aid the cure of the resin. The power source was a pneumatic pistol-grip drill driven by a portable compressor unit. The only concession to laboratory procedure was the weighing of the resin components on a local balance rather than mixing them from prepackaged, calibrated containers as would be available from a custom-built repair kit. The resin used for both repairs was Quickcure 3 polyester cured with 1½ per cent Butanox M50.

The under-wing repair

The periphery of the hole was abraded to a distance of 100 mm all round with a flap-wheel. One face of the rib was similarly abraded. The total abrasion time was 35 minutes. A piece of wire mesh was cut, fitted to the unabraded face of the rib, and held in place across the gap by bending the free ends of the mesh (Fig 13). A 150 mm wide strip of unidirectional carbon fibre tape was folded in half length-wise and wet-laminated across the abraded face of the rib to form a patch two plies thick. A total time of nine minutes was taken for the meshing and laminating operations on the rib.

In the next operation, the repair of the skin, a rectangle of wire mesh 25 mm larger all round than the hole was inserted through it, opened out flat and held in place against the inner surface with five 'pop' rivets fitted with backing washers. This was facilitated by making two crossed cuts in the centre of the rectangle and opening them out to allow the insertion of the operator's hand; after rivetting the opened-out mesh was bent back into place (Fig 14). The meshing operation took 10 minutes.

A rectangle of hybrid fabric was cut 100 mm larger all round than the hole, feathered 12 mm back at the edges by removing free tows, and laid flat on a sheet of paper. Three more rectangles each successively 12.5 mm smaller all round were cut, feathered and stacked on top of the first.

A rectangular pad of flexible foam 40 mm thick and larger than the largest patch was laid flat and covered with a sheet of fluorinated ethylene propylene (FEP) parting film. The top patch, the smallest, was taken from the stack, laid centrally on the film, and well impregnated with resin. The remaining three patches were added in order squarely and centrally over the first and were also well impregnated. A coat of resin was brushed on to the abraded area around the hole, and the patch on its foam support was raised into position against the

wing surface on a piece of hardboard (Fig 15). An attempt was made to support the assembly by means of improvised props, but this caused the patch to slide sideways across the wing and was abandoned; the assembly was supported manually for seven minutes until the resin had gelled.

The tendency for the patch to slide sideways was very marked. It had not been anticipated, and no guidelines had been drawn on the wing so that it could be seen and corrected. It was disappointing to find when the support was removed that the patch was perfectly finished and flat but was well off centre (Fig 16).

The carbon-fibre patch across the rib was not intended to be a full-strength repair but was included for experience and timing. The wire mesh backing to the main repair was also included for experience and timing; it would not normally be required for a repair to an under-wing area because the patch is supported by the foam pad.

A satisfactory method of positively locating the patch was tested on a simulated aircraft under-wing. The supporting hardboard was first modified by the addition of a 6 mm hole at each corner. The hardboard was then placed centrally over the damage area, the positions of the holes were marked on the under-wing surface, the board was removed and the marked positions abraded down to the bare metal to receive adhesive. Bighead studs were placed head-uppermost in the holes in the hardboard and cyanoacrylate "instant" adhesive was applied to the upper surfaces of their heads. The board was raised into the original position, held against the structure for one minute to allow the glue to set, and lowered leaving the studs in place. The wet-laminated patch was built up on the foam pad and hardboard as before, and applied by locating the hardboard once more onto the studs and retaining it there by wing nuts. After gelation the nuts were released, the hardboard and pad lowered, and the studs knocked loose from the structure.

The fuselage repair

To simulate emergency conditions this repair was done without power tools. The projecting metal was beaten back into place and a plug to fit the hole (Fig 17) was cut from a block of Rohacell 70 rigid foam. In practice, a hole in a vertical surface would not require bridging; where this was essential a lighter foam such as Rohacell 30 would have been preferable.

A square area round the hole was abraded by hand to a width of 75 mm instead of the 100 mm recommended for power abrasion, since this had been shown (Table 3) to give an adhesion adequate for the area being repaired. The three different available models of hand abrader A (Fig 8) were used, and they and the surface being abraded were frequently rinsed with water to remove the paint dust. A good abrasion down to the bare metal was obtained in 50 minutes.

Because the fuselage was wet with rain the resin-wipe technique was used. A coat of resin was painted on to the abraded area and immediately wiped off with a clean paper towel. A second coat of resin was applied, and four patches of hybrid cloth, cut and feathered as for the underwing repair, were wet-laminated directly on to the fuselage in order of decreasing size. After laminating the patch was supported manually for 5 minutes to prevent it sliding.

The finished repair is shown in Fig 18. The total time taken was one hour and ten minutes.

THE REPAIR OF A HYDRAULIC JACK

A Canberra flap actuator jack with a damaged barrel was received for repair. The damage consisted of a single irregular hole approximately at the centre of the barrel (Fig 19) surrounded by a number of indentations.

The jack was placed in a vice with the hole uppermost and the painted exterior of the barrel was abraded down to the bare metal. The hole was plugged to prevent laminating resin from entering the barrel, using a small quantity of the fast-curing epoxy resin mix Epikote 828:Curing agent 1537/100:50, which was pressed into the hole and allowed to cure (5 minutes). The plug was then abraded down to match the contour of the barrel.

Because the efficiency of the repair would depend on the stiffness of the patch in the hoop direction an all-carbon 5-shaft satin weave fabric was used, based on Grafil EXAS 3000-filament tow; a strip was cut to fit the width of the centre section of the barrel and long enough to wrap $4\frac{1}{2}$ times round it. The surface of the barrel was wiped as free as possible from hydraulic fluid and the end of the carbon-fibre tape was fastened with a narrow strip of self-adhesive vinyl tape to the side of the barrel in a position that would allow five thicknesses of tape to cover the hole after wrap-round.

The tape was wet-laminated around the barrel using Quickcure 3/Butanox M50 resin, maintained under continuous hand tension to ensure a tight wrap, and finally held in place with a light overwrap of sewing cotton. The double-wipe technique was not used because it would be difficult to apply to a jack in situ. The total time taken for the repair was 35 minutes; the finished repair is shown in Fig 20.

It was not possible to test the repair after 4 hours because of the location of the equipment. Tested after 24 hours it withstood repeated cycling to 2200 lbf/in^2 (15.2 MN/m^2) including dwells of up to ten minutes at that pressure. The first leakage occurred at a rate of 6 drops/min after 30 minutes. On lowering the pressure to 1800 lbf/in^2 (12.4 MN/m^2) the leakage ceased and did not recur during a 15 minute dwell. The repair was judged by the aircraft maintenance crew to be fully acceptable for emergency operation.

THE USE OF PRE-CURED FABRIC LAMINATE PATCHES

Complementary to published work [4] on the use of pre-formed, pre-cured patches based on aligned pre-preg, it was decided to investigate the use of similar patches based on carbon-fibre fabric, since these present certain advantages over pre-preg patches, notably the ability to accommodate greater double curvatures during fabrication without the appearance of gaps between fibre tows, and a greater reproducibility of alignment.

A Jetstream aircraft which had developed cracks during fatigue testing was available for repair. The cracks were situated at the inboard end of the trailing edge of the port wing, and extended inward and outward for $1\frac{1}{2}$ mm each side of a rivet-hole. A 75×25 mm pre-cured patch, fabricated from 8 plies of 3000-filament five-shaft satin weave Grafil EXAS fabric and XD 927 resin and chamfered at each end, was bonded across the cracks and the flush head of the rivet. The adhesive used was Hysol 9309, and cure was effected by a hot air-stream.

The aircraft was subjected to six weeks continuous fatigue testing, equivalent to 3000 flights, after which the patch was removed for inspection. No measurable crack growth had occurred.

In parallel laboratory experiments similar patches were bonded to aluminium alloy panels across the widths of which cracks were growing under fluctuating tensile fatigue from the ends of spark-eroded cuts. Depending on the quality, configuration and bonding technique, crack growth was retarded or arrested completely, demonstrating the extremely efficient transfer of load through the patch. Work is in hand to optimize the parameters and a full report will be presented elsewhere.

CONCLUSIONS

The work described in this paper has demonstrated that wet-laminating repair techniques can be employed on contaminated surfaces, under adverse environmental conditions, and without heat. Good adhesion can be obtained by preparing the substrate with simple abrasion alone provided it is done thoroughly.

A number of alternative resin systems can be used. Polyesters are easier to use than epoxies since they wet-out the fabric better at low temperatures and their shorter gel times lessen the possibility of the repair deforming under gravity while still wet. Their repair strengths are not as high as those obtained from epoxies, but are still superior to those of metal plate repairs fastened with 'pop' rivets at 15 mm spacing.

Work is currently in hand to investigate the strength of repairs done at 0°C.

Our wish to carry out emergency repairs entirely without heat has been a severe limitation; if a modest heat source were available a much wider range of resins could be used.

Satisfactory results including complete crack arrest have been obtained from the application of pre-cured carbon-fibre fabric laminate patches to the control of fatigue cracks in light alloy, both in the laboratory and in ground test on an actual aircraft.

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TABLE 1

COMPARISON OF RESIN SYSTEMS; TENSILE STRENGTHS OF
SIMULATION-REPAIRS TO L73 ALLOY SHEET AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

3:1 glass:carbon plain-weave fabric

Resin system	Time from start of repair (h)	No of repairs	Mean tensile strength (kN)	Coeff. of variation (%)
Epikote 828/Ancamine AC	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	4	11.7	12
	24	3	12.3	5
	72	2	11.9	14
Epikote 808/Ancamine AC	3 $\frac{1}{2}$	2	8.8	10
	24	2	11.7	3
	72	2	12.7	3
Epikote 828/Mercaptan 301B	2	1	7.8	
	4	1	9.3	
	24	1	10.5	
Epoxy resin ER2/Mercaptan 301B	2	1	8.6	
	4	1	9.8	
	24	1	10.9	
Quickcure 1/Butanox M50	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	4	7.5	16
	24	4	7.4	8
	72	4	6.4	12
Quickcure 3/Butanox M50	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	9	6.9	19
	24	9	8.3	12
	72	8	8.1	15
Quickcure 3/Lucidol CH50/ dimethyl p-toluidine	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	2	7.3	9
	24	2	8.0	3
	72	1	8.0	
Cellobond A260/Butanox M50	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	2	7.2	8
	24	2	7.3	5
	72	2	6.6	16
Trylon AP101PA/Butanox M50/ accelerator NL 49	2 $\frac{1}{2}$	2	5.8	11
	24	2	7.8	11
	72	2	7.4	2

TABLE 2

TENSILE STRENGTHS OF SIMULATION-REPAIRS TO PAINTED L72 ALLOY SHEET
AFTER INCOMPLETE ABRASION

Weathered acrylic finish; Quickcure 3/Butanox M50 resin; 3:1 glass:carbon plain-weave fabric.

Surface treatment	Time from start of repair (h)	Tensile strength (kN)
Acetone-wiped with paper towel	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	2.0 ; 2.4
	24	2.3 ; 3.6
	72	3.0 ; 2.7
Lightly abraded with 80 mm x 30 mm 80 grade flap wheel	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	3.2 ; 3.5
	24	3.2 ; 3.2
	72	3.3 ; 3.8
Abraded down to primer, using coarse abrasive block	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	3.3 ; 3.3
	24	6.2 ; 5.8
	72	6.3 ; 5.7
Abraded down to bare metal with 80 mm x 30 mm 80 grade flap wheel	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	6.0 ; 6.3
	24	8.2 ; 7.6
	72	6.8 ; 7.3

TABLE 3

COMPARISON OF THE TENSILE STRENGTHS OF 75 mm AND
100 mm PATCH OVERLAP BOND LENGTHS

Repair temperature 20°C

Contaminant	Resin	Overlap (mm)	Time from start. (h)	Tensile Strength	Mean Strength Loss (%)
None	Epikote 828/Ancamine AC (repairs at 16°C)	100	4	7.8 ; 9.0	
			24	11.4 ; 11.8	
			72	12.0 ; 13.0	
		75	4	7.0 ; 7.2	
			24	8.4 ; 9.8	
			72	10.6 ; 10.4	
	Quickcure 3/Butanox M50	100	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	9.0 ; 9.0	
			24	9.2 ; 8.6	
			72	9.5 ; 9.3	
75		2 $\frac{1}{4}$	8.4 ; 7.1		
		24	9.7 ; 9.1		
		72	10.3 ; 9.1		
Hydraulic fluid	Epikote 828/Ancamine AC	100	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	9.3 ; 10.0	
			24	5.3 ; 5.7	
			72	5.5 ; 4.5	
		75	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	8.7 ; 10.1	
			24	5.0 ; 5.0	
			72	5.2 ; 6.0	
	Quickcure 3/Butanox M50	100	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	7.6 ; 7.8	
			24	8.8 ; 8.1	
			72	6.8 ; 6.6	
		75	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	5.8 ; 6.3	
			24	8.1 ; 7.9	
			72	6.7 ; 6.1	
Avtur 50	Epikote 828/Ancamine AC	100	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	12.8 ; 13.2	
			24	13.4 ; 12.0	
			72	13.0 ; 11.6	
		75	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	12.8 ; 12.8	
			24	10.7 ; 12.2	
			72	12.6 ; 11.4	
	Quickcure 3/Butanox M50	100	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	9.2 ; 8.8	
			24	8.9 ; 9.5	
			72	8.8 ; 7.8	
		75	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	6.4 ; 6.3	
			24	7.6 ; 7.2	
			72	7.5 ; 7.6	
Water.	Quickcure 3/Butanox M50	100	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	6.6 ; 7.3	
			24	6.3 ; 6.7	
			72	6.6 ; 7.1	
		75	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	5.5 ; 5.6	
			24	6.5 ; 7.2	
			72	7.4 ; 7.5	

TABLE 5

TENSILE STRENGTHS OF SIMULATION-REPAIRS TO CONTAMINATED L73 SHEET

100 mm bond overlap; 3:1 glass:carbon plain-weave fabric

Contaminant	Resin	Time from start of repair (h)	No. of repairs	Mean tensile strength (kN)	Coeff. of variation (%)
Hydraulic fluid	Epikote 828/Ancamine AC	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	2	10.1	6
		24	2	5.4	4
		72	2	5.4	10
	Quickcure 3/Butanox M50	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	1	7.7	
		24	1	8.5	
		72	1	6.7	
	Quickcure 3/Lucidol CH50/ dimethyl p-toluidine	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	2	8.4	11
		24	2	7.3	3
		72	2	7.4	7
Avtur 50	Epikote 828/Ancamine AC	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	1	13.0	
		24	1	12.7	
		72	1	12.3	
	Quickcure 3/Butanox M50	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	1	9.0	
		24	1	9.2	
		72	1	8.3	
	Quickcure 3/Lucidol CH50/ dimethyl p-toluidine	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	2	7.9	3
		24	2	7.6	5
		72	2	7.9	4
Water	Epikote 828/Ancamine AC	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	2	9.1	26
		24	2	10.5	20
		72	2	10.4	19
	Quickcure 3/Butanox M50	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	1	7.0	
		24	1	6.5	
		72	1	6.9	
	Quickcure 3/Lucidol CH50/ dimethyl p-toluidine	2 $\frac{1}{4}$	1	5.6	
		24	1	7.7	
		72	1	6.5	

TABLE 4

RELATIVE EFFICIENCIES OF ABRASION DEVICES

Time to completely remove a 60 mm square of weathered paint

Device	Time (sec)	Device	Time (sec)
<u>Power operated</u>		<u>Hand operated</u>	
Flap wheel		Abrader A	
2400 rev/min	80 mm dia 80 grade	fine	80
	95 mm dia 60 grade	coarse	100
	60 mm dia 80 grade	Abrader B	
900 rev/min	80 mm dia 80 grade	coarse	355
	95 mm dia 60 grade	medium	360
	80 mm dia 60 grade	Abrader C	
	60 mm dia 80 grade	coarse	400
Disc sander			
	125 mm dia		
	78 mm dia		
Rotary flail			
	coarse flail wires		
	fine flail wires		

TABLE 6

TENSILE STRENGTHS OF SIMULATION-REPAIRS TO L73 SHEET
BELOW ROOM TEMPERATURE

3:1 glass:carbon unidirectional fabric

Resin	Temperature (°C)	Time from start of repair (h)	Tensile strength (kN)
Polyester AP101PA/Butanox M50	9.5	3	8.7; 8.6
		24	11.5; 10.1
		72	11.1; 10.2
	7	4	6.1; 7.0
		24	7.9; 8.4
		48	8.2; 8.5
Epikote 808/Ancamine AC	7	4	not yet cured
		21½	12.2; 9.9
		49	8.8; 11.3
Polyester BIP874/Butanox M50	1	72	5.1; 8.2
		4	6.1; 7.0
		24	7.9; 8.4
		48	8.2; 8.5

Fig 1 3:1 glass:carbon plain weave hybrid fabric patch feathered ready for laminating.

Fig 2 Basic repair stage (a); the damaged component.

Fig 3 Basic repair stage (b); the hole bridged on the reverse side with wire mesh.

Fig 4 Basic repair stage (c); the finished repair.

Fig 5 The simulation-repair test; - schematic.

Fig 6 Wire cup brush in used condition.

Fig 7 Rotary flap wheel abraders.

Fig 8 Coarse and fine hand abraders type A.

Fig 9 Helicopter drive shaft after abrasion.

Fig 10 Helicopter drive shaft; - the completed repair.

Fig 11 Canberra aircraft; - the fuselage damage.

Fig 12 Canberra aircraft; - the under-wing damage.

Fig 13 The rib bridged with unidirectional carbon fibre fabric.

Fig 14 The hole bridged with wire mesh.

Fig 15 Applying the under-wing patch.

Fig 16 The completed under-wing repair.

Fig 17 The fuselage hole with plug inserted.

Fig 18 The completed fuselage repair.

Fig 19 Hydraulic jack:- detail of damage.

Fig 20 Hydraulic jack:- the completed repair.